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Abstract

This paper explores how trans masculine people living in Ireland perceive and engage with representations of trans identities in different outlets of popular offline media. Drawing on qualitative interviews from 2019 with seven Irish trans masculine individuals, aged 19-37, this study explores these participants' perceptions of offline media representations of trans people as overwhelmingly sensationalist and reductionist, while investigating the meaningful ways they have been able to engage with limited nuanced representations. Placed within the cultural context of contemporary Ireland, this article examines the tensions these participants described between popular narratives of transnormative gender identities and their own lived experiences of gender. This study's findings suggest that reductionist and tokenistic offline media representations of trans identities were regarded as harmful and devaluing of these individuals' experiences, while select nuanced representations were used as sites of self-reflection and initiating dialogue with others. The majority of participants agreed that trans representation in offline media could play an influential role in shaping individual experiences and expressions of trans masculinity and conveyed their desire for more varied trans representation in Irish and international offline media.

Key words: trans masculinities; queer; media; representation; Ireland

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Introduction

As trans individuals have gained greater visibility in the global mediascape, alarmist views around trans identities have become fixtures in international news publications and broadcasts. On the world's most popular news platforms, the validity of trans experiences is commonly presented as the subject of polarising media debates - debates which, as Faye (2021) describes, have become both "poisonous" and "banal" (14). International television and film, meanwhile, has shifted to incorporate more sympathetic portrayals of trans individuals, yet these portrayals usually rely on long-established media tropes and lack the input and artistry of the very people they attempt to represent (Copier and Steinbock, 2018). In this article, I explore how trans masculine people living in Ireland perceive and engage with varying representations of trans identities in different outlets of popular offline media. Drawing on qualitative interviews from 2019, this study examines seven Irish trans masculine individuals' perceptions of offline media representations of trans people as overwhelmingly sensationalist and reductionist, while investigating the meaningful ways they have been able to engage with nuanced representations. Discussing participants' impressions of existing trans representation and its uses and limits, this article explores how these Irish trans masculine individuals have contended with the invisibility of nonnormative trans identities in offline media and how popular narratives of transnormative gender identities have influenced their lived experiences of trans masculinity.

There is a fair amount of existing research detailing the ways *online* media has been a platform through which trans people form a positive sense of gender identity, as well as build digital trans communities (Haimson et al., 2021; Cavalcante, 2019; Jenzen, 2017; Green et al., 2015; Beemyn and Rankin, 2011). This study does not further investigate online media use, but instead examines engagement with *offline media*—a term which, for the purpose of this article, encompasses elements of popular culture such as television, film, radio, books, newspapers, and video games—in view of the wider accessibility to, and passive consumption of, such media. Whereas queer community building online is a purposeful act and social media representations of trans identities are usually curated by trans people themselves, offline media frequently presents itself without being sought out and offline media representations of queerness are most often produced by cisgender creators (Billard and Zhang, 2022). In fact, existing studies of trans individuals' reception to trans representation have shown that offline media can be where they first encounter examples of trans identities, sometimes even initiating processes of self-identification (McInroy and Craig, 2015; Heinz, 2011). Upon designing this study, I considered how the ongoing hybridisation of offline and online media (i.e. television streaming platforms, podcasts, and digital newspapers) has blurred the boundaries between these previously distinct categories. Therefore, although, by definition, traditional offline media is distinguished from media on the internet, for the purposes of this article offline media includes any traditional offline media form, whether consumed on or off digital platforms.

While recent years have seen an increase in research around trans masculine representations in media of varying forms, this research has focused primarily on the analysis of texts that include representations of trans masculine identities and their potential for bolstering or disrupting normative understandings of gender (Keegan,

2022; Korobacz and Cook, 2022; Steinbock, 2019; Halberstam, 2018; Lovelock, 2017; Heinz, 2016; Johnson, 2016; Riggs, 2014; MocarSKI et al., 2013). There is a notable lack of in-depth studies which focus particularly on trans masculine individuals' own perceptions and analyses of trans media. This project, therefore, focuses on the media engagement of an underrepresented trans masculine population. As Irish scholarship is especially lacking in studies of regional trans masculine experiences, the present study aims to contribute to broader understandings of the experiences of individual trans masculine people in Ireland by investigating their engagement with offline media representations of trans identities, as well as the impact that this content has had on their senses of identity and expressions of masculinity.

Trans identities and masculinities

The use of “trans” in this article follows Whittle (2006: xi), who describes how identification with “trans” is accessible “to anyone who does not feel comfortable in the gender role they were attributed with at birth” or else experiences gender in a way “at odds with the labels ‘man’ or ‘woman’ credited to them by formal authorities” (xi). Recent scholarship around trans identities has taken up Halberstam’s proposed “trans*” (Halberstam, 2018). In Halberstam’s view, the addition of the asterisk opens the term to “unfolding categories of being organized around but not confined to forms of gender variance” (4). Halberstam’s “trans*” does not have a “destination” or “final form” that takes shape through social legitimisation or medicalisation (4). As Halberstam describes:

The asterisk holds off the certainty of diagnosis; it keeps at bay any sense of knowing in advance what the meaning of this or that gender variant form may be, and perhaps most importantly, it makes trans* people the authors of their own categorizations (Halberstam, 2018: 4).

While I leave off the asterisk here in keeping with the written language used by myself and participants throughout the original processes of the study, the use of “trans” in this article is still a deliberately expansive move that indicates the experiences of individuals who are positioned within specific gender identity categories (i.e: transgender and transsexual), as well as those with fluid, less-definable experiences of gender. In this spirit, throughout the study design I aimed to keep the terminology relatively unconfined by strict identity labels. However, as this research explores queer masculinities specifically, I use “trans masculine” in this study to encompass the varying and intersecting experiences of trans individuals who were assigned female at birth and understand their gender as relating to masculinity. In this study, the individuals interviewed indicated identification with various gender identities, including trans man, FTM (female to male), and butch, and many of these individuals described their gender as belonging in multiple, overlapping categories of masculine gender experience.

The individuals interviewed for this study each had distinct ways of “doing gender” (West and Zimmerman, 1987) that grappled with normative expectations of masculinity. As West and Zimmerman’s theory describes, gender is not a biologically determined truth, but rather, an accomplishment of everyday interaction. Those who successfully “do gender” adopt the normative behaviours and values attributed to

masculinity or femininity, which are in themselves norms attributed to the sex categories of male and female. Doing gender in this way continually legitimises the institutionalisation of a “natural” gender and sex alignment (West and Zimmerman, 1987). In their seminal work on gender performativity, Butler (1990) also describes gender as an active “doing” which gives the appearance of inherent, fixed identity (33). In Butler’s theorisation, gender identity is how individuals position themselves as gendered in relation to other gendered individuals, and through the repeated performance of gendered acts - acts which are viewed as the “results” of identity (Butler, 1990: 33). It is through such repetition of gendered acts that gender norms are reinforced within culturally institutionalised systems of gender categorisation. Yet individuals whose experiences of gender diverge from cultural norms, such as those interviewed for this study, complicate rigid gender categories, and thus can challenge the maintenance of gender and sexuality hierarchies.

As this article centres representations of trans masculinity, the framework of “hegemonic masculinity”, Connell’s (1987) foundational contribution to the field of Critical Studies of Men and Masculinities, is employed to investigate hierarchies within representations of masculinities. As Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) describe, social groups are hierarchised within regionally specific gender orders and hegemonic masculinity is the idealised image of masculinity upheld within this hierarchy, constructed in relation to “subordinated masculinities” and femininities. This ideal, hegemonic form of masculinity is reproduced in western popular culture, and, as Beasley (2008) suggests, should be viewed as an “enabling mode of representation, which mobilizes institutions and practices” in society (94). Recent scholarship which views trans masculinity within the framework of hegemonic masculinity has explored how trans masculine individuals do gender in ways that can both ascribe to the regulatory gender order as well as challenge it (Vidal-Ortiz, 2005; Abelson, 2019; Aboim and Vasconcelos, 2021; Rubin, 2003). In Vidal-Ortiz’s (2005) interviews with American trans masculine individuals, many of them expressed actively opposing normative values of hegemonic masculinity, while also describing the benefits of being perceived as men within this gender hierarchy (192). The participants of the present study expressed similar tensions within their experiences of masculinity, which will be explored further below.

Queer representation in Ireland

Many of the offline media representations of trans identities described by participants were viewed by them as perpetuating values of traditional Irish society, especially heteronormativity and cisnormativity. Heteronormativity, as defined by Berlant and Warner (1998), is “the project of normalization that has made heterosexuality hegemonic” (548). In other words, it is the belief and construction of heterosexuality as the normative, natural state (Rosenfeld, 2009). However, as Ahmed (2004) describes, heteronormativity refers to more than the assumption that heterosexuality is “normal”; it is, in fact, a regulatory force (149). Heterosexuality is institutionalised, and the discourses produced through regional systems of religion, medicine, and government reinforce a hierarchy in which non-heterosexual behaviours are considered deviant and, therefore, controlled and suppressed (Ingraham, 2005; Elia, 2003). Cisnormativity, in a similar vein, refers to the institutionalised, normative ideology of the sex and gender binary. In societies structured by cisnormativity, it is assumed that every person identifies with the sex

category (either “male” or “female”) that is assigned to them at birth (Rydström, 2020). In a recent study with trans and gender diverse youth in Ireland, institutionalised cisnormativity in schools was shown to stigmatise these children and leave them vulnerable to harassment, violence, and educational inequality (McBride and Neary, 2021). McBride and Neary suggest that school policies perpetuate “non-recognition and non-representation” (2021: 1098) of gender diversity, and this systemic lack of visibility contributes to anti-trans stigma. While international media has begun to feature more trans storylines and characters, my conversations with study participants exposed a perceived lack of acceptance from general Irish society due to cis/heteronormative popular media, which portrays nonnormative genders and sexualities through a regulatory lens.

The emergence of queer visibility in the Irish cultural imaginary is a relatively recent phenomenon. I use “queer” here, in keeping with Sedgwick’s guiding definition, to refer to:

the open mesh of possibilities, gaps, overlaps, dissonances and resonances, lapses and excesses of meaning when the constituent elements of anyone’s gender, or anyone’s sexuality aren’t made (or can’t be made) to signify monolithically (Sedgwick, 2012: 338).

The Republic of Ireland, a nation which, under British colonisation, had outlawed homosexuality until the 1990s, has historically been viewed as a monolithic society with Catholic, heteronormative, and sexually conservative values (Conrad, 2001). In May 2015, the marriage referendum proposal was passed by a large majority of Irish voters and the definition of marriage in the constitution was broadened to introduce marriage equality for gay and lesbian couples (Elkink et al., 2017). In a study investigating voting patterns in the 2015 Marriage Referendum, Elkink et al. posit that post-vote survey findings indicate a “slowly dying conservative Ireland” (2017: 377). From this viewpoint, the introduction of same-sex marriage into law was the sign of an increasingly progressive government and a generally more open-minded Irish population. However, the sizeable “Vote No” campaign against same-sex marriage, backed by nationalist, religious organisations that emphasised “traditional” family values, reflected significant resistance to nonnormative sexualities and genders through “heteroactivism”, what Browne, Nash and Gorman-Murray (2018) define as a “form of activism that seeks to recuperate hegemonic heteronormativities where sexual and gender rights are in place” (6). Further, as advocates for same-sex marriage promoted social legitimisation through the legal institution of marriage, the voting majority’s seemingly broad-minded acceptance of gay and lesbian individuals can be viewed as largely contingent on their assimilation into normative, heterosexual Irish society (Neary, 2016). This reproduction of normative institutions and values exemplifies what Duggan has coined “homonormativity”, a politics that upholds heteronormativity and limits potential for any radical, queer reimaging of social structures (Duggan, 2003).

Even as media surrounding these debates placed (some) nonnormative sexualities more firmly into public consciousness, representations of varied queer experiences remained absent from Irish broadcasting until recent years. From the time that homosexuality was decriminalised in 1993, until the establishment of the Marriage Equality Act in 2015, popular “queer” media discourse centred homonormative gay and lesbian identities and featured only rare coverage of trans issues, as with the case

of Lydia Foy, a trans woman who fought from 1997 to have her gender legally recognised through twenty years of legal proceedings (Kerrigan, 2020: 167). More recently, trans identities have become increasingly visible through media debates around gender and sexuality. Neary (2018) cites the debates surrounding the 2015 Gender Recognition Act—legislation which enabled trans people to obtain legal recognition of their genders in Ireland—as fixing trans individuals more prominently into the Irish cultural imaginary. Kerrigan (2020) similarly cites this legislation as the catalyst for the introduction of trans storylines in Irish television. This phenomenon is not unique to Ireland, and, as Copier and Steinbock (2018) suggest, the frequency with which trans stories and characters have begun to appear in popular media may be linked to international movements towards trans rights (923).

Popular representations of trans identities

While many recent media representations of trans identities are celebratory examples of trans lives and are more frequently created by trans actors and artists (Pearce et al., 2018), tokenistic storylines based on stereotypes continue to be applied to trans characters in international film and television (Lefevre, 2021; McLaren et al., 2021). Meanwhile, western news coverage around gender diversity continues to present trans-exclusionary ideologies as one side of a reasoned, political debate (McLaren et al., 2021; Pearce et al., 2020). In Ireland specifically, even as trans people experience unprecedented levels of visibility and representation, the legal rights of trans individuals remain debating points within popular media discourse (Kerrigan, 2021: 55-56). Further, while the participants of the present study described engaging with offline media on a regular basis, most described struggling to find or engage with trans masculine representation. Recent scholarship on trans media representation has found that trans masculine people are less represented in media than trans feminine people (Capuzza and Spencer, 2017; Feder and Juhasz, 2016; Heinz, 2016; Keegan, 2016). Trans actress and writer Jen Richards describes this phenomenon in Sam Feder’s documentary *Disclosure* (2020):

Trans women vastly outnumber trans men in terms of depictions and portrayals in the media, uh, even though the numbers, the actual numbers, of real trans people are pretty evenly split between men and women, just like with cis people, but we see far more depictions of trans women. And, of course, that’s partly because women overall, therefore including trans women, are a more commodifiable asset (Feder, 2020).

As the documentary goes on to highlight, this commodification of trans individuals does not necessarily combat transphobia off-screen (2020). In fact, the growth of trans visibility in media has been shown to have occurred in parallel to increased anti-trans violence, especially towards trans people of colour (Faye 2021; Stanley, 2021; cárdenas 2019). In their recent collection on trans cultural production, Gossett, Stanley, and Burton theorise the increased media visibility of trans individuals as a “trap door”, due to this corresponding escalation of anti-trans violence (2019). While media representation is often presented as the way forward for trans people to have “livable lives” (Gossett et al., 2019: xv), these representations of trans identities are almost always compliant with cis/heteronormative models for expressing gender and sexuality. The media’s successful commodification of these

specific trans experiences has further established industry standards for representing marketable trans people (Keegan, 2022). This standardisation of trans representation also upholds whiteness through what Gossett calls “neoliberal trans visibility and respectability politics” (Gossett, 2019: 183), in which the authentic experiences of trans individuals who are otherwise marginalised due to race, class, disability, and other social categorisations are omitted from mainstream media. In effect, by essentialising a normative trans experience, popular media operates to further marginalise trans individuals who do not assimilate to this experience.

The representation of an essential trans experience can be viewed as a feature of transnormativity, which Johnson (2016) defines as “a hegemonic ideology that structures transgender experience, identification, and narratives into a hierarchy of legitimacy” (466). This hierarchy privileges a binary, medical model of trans experience, in which a trans person seeks gender-affirming medical care such as surgeries and hormone therapy in order to embody physical traits that are traditionally associated with a specific gender (Johnson, 2016). This model of trans experience is most often depicted in media, while the experiences of trans individuals who do not wish to pursue, or cannot acquire, medical interventions are left unrepresented. As Johnson shows, the mainstreaming of this model contributes to social and systemic regulation of trans individuals’ bodies (2016). While many of the participants in the present study had sought or received gender-affirming medical care, most expressed a sense of disconnection with representations of trans identities wrought through the regulatory ideology of transnormativity, and for those individuals, this contributed to feelings of inadequacy or isolation.

Methods and methodology

Drawing on data gathered through in-depth qualitative interviews, this study explores how seven trans masculine individuals in Ireland perceived and engaged with offline media representations of trans identities, and how they positioned themselves in relation to this media. While a research project of this size has limitations such as sampling bias, similarly-sized qualitative studies of trans individuals’ experiences note that such research is valuable for its ability to cultivate rich data (Rogers, 2017). As with Rogers (2017), this study does not intend to universalise the experiences and perceptions of these individuals into a narrative of “trans experience”, but rather, to make “significant distinctions” (Aspers and Corte, 2019) of the ways individual trans masculine people experience engagement with trans representation in offline media. As these interviews would potentially touch on sensitive topics, including violence against trans individuals in both the media and reality, ethical considerations were given serious attention and care throughout the design of the study. Ethical approval to conduct this study was granted by the Ethics Committee of the School of Histories and Humanities at Trinity College Dublin. All names and personal identifiers have been anonymised to protect the privacy of the participants.

The findings presented here are from a larger mixed-methods study and based on qualitative data from interviews conducted in 2019. Study participants were initially recruited through purposive and snowball sampling techniques via an online survey also used to collect primary quantitative data while reaching participants located throughout Ireland. The survey was posted on a Tumblr blog and shared with

LGBTQI+ social groups, networks, and virtual platforms based in Ireland, and viewers were encouraged to share the survey with other potential participants. Seven trans masculine individuals were recruited. These individuals indicated a variety of gender identities, including gendervoid, non-binary, and butch. Participants ranged in age from 19 to 37 years. All of the participants were white. Out of the seven participants, two were in third-level education, and two were postgraduate students. These four participants were all based in metropolitan areas of Ireland such as Cork, Limerick, and Dublin. Of the other three participants, one was in vocational education, one was unemployed, and one was a craft worker. These three participants were based in small towns in rural Ireland. I conducted each of the qualitative interviews during July and August 2019, in the locations where participants resided.

This research was designed in consideration of the complex relationship of power which would exist between myself and the participants—a relationship influenced by my own non-trans identity and my position as researcher. I therefore adopted an open-ended, semi-structured interview approach to build a level of trust and bond with the participants, with the intention of making them feel safe and supported enough to allow me insight into their lifeworlds (Brinkmann, 2014: 438). This approach was embraced with the goal of democratising the research interview space and allowing meaning to emerge through the “unfolding interactions of the interview” (Gorman-Murray et al., 2010: 101). Participants were therefore encouraged to guide the direction of the interview and discuss matters they considered most meaningful or interesting. In line with the approach of Abelson (2019), who, as a non-trans researcher, illustrates the importance of centring the voices of trans participants, I wanted to ensure that I was facilitating organic conversations where participants felt able to speak openly, so that any quotes I analysed were in keeping with their genuine perspectives. Therefore, although I had prepared a general interview guide, this remained unfixed throughout the study as each interview took shape, reflecting individual perceptions of trans masculine experiences in Ireland and the ways these experiences related to offline media representations of trans identities.

As a non-trans researcher, I am mindful of how cisnormativity has benefited me personally and informed my learning and worldview in complex and persistent ways. As a queer person, I also have personal investment in the construction of a better world for queer individuals, which has naturally led me towards such research. I approached analysis with this awareness of my position and a commitment to centring the voices of participants and reflecting their experiences with honesty and transparency. The interviews were transcribed verbatim and analysed using the data analysis software *ATLAS.ti*. The data was analysed using thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2012), an approach which commenced with a familiarisation phase, in which I listened to the audio recordings, went over the transcripts, and made notes, guided by the general question, ‘How do trans masculine individuals in Ireland engage with and relate to trans representation in offline media?’. Employing an inductive approach, I then began establishing descriptive codes from the “bottom-up” (Braun and Clarke, 2012: 58), identifying codes and themes from the data. In this phase, I used codes that mirrored participants’ language to organise sections of data while remaining close to the participants’ points of view (i.e. “feeling seen”, “proper way to be trans” and “toxic masculinity”). These codes were then further analysed to identify commonalities and repetitions throughout the data, while

exploring the tensions within the ways these individuals understood and engaged with offline media representations of trans identities. Themes were generated, reviewed, and defined around these patterns and complexities.

Sensationalist and reductionist offline media representations of trans identities

While recent years have seen an unprecedented increase in trans representation in offline media (Pearce et al., 2018), during interviews, each of the seven participants expressed the belief that there is scarce offline media representation of trans people, especially trans masculine people. While perceived as exceptional, instances of nuanced representations of trans identities were reported to have had a positive impact on some participants' sense of self. Conversely, ridiculing, demeaning representations, which were described as more frequent, had a reportedly strong impact on participants as well. A typical example of trans representation on television, according to Ben, was when "some cis man in a dress plays a trans woman" with "some joke involving slurs". Although celebratory representations of trans individuals in entertainment media have increased on a global scale, trans representations through these mediums have historically and persistently been transphobic (Heinz, 2016) and contemporary news media continually features anti-trans debates and rhetoric (Slothouber, 2020). Faye (2021) expands on this phenomenon in the British context, describing how trans people have been positioned as dangerous ideologists in popular UK media outlets, which release content centring the "transgender issue" daily (6). Participants spoke of the lasting impact such sensationalist media coverage has had on them personally:

It can be very hard to see, like, where does your future go if every story about someone like you has this negative gloom over it or how so often trans people are portrayed as victims and stuff like that, or criminals and stuff like that... That can be hard on you if you never see someone succeeding (Zach, he/him, 19, metropolitan Ireland).

I don't really watch much TV. There was a program I used to watch a couple of years ago, I don't remember what it was called, but I still remember them making a laugh out of trans people. That felt bad, and so now I don't really watch many programmes (Oliver, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

Elle, who described her gender as both trans masculine and butch woman, described her concern for younger gender-variant people, due to the way their identities have been presented as debatable through the mainstream media accessed by their parents:

I do worry about young, trans and nonbinary kids. Just because of what's being portrayed and the kind of the narratives they're getting fed [...] But it is a worry, because a lot of it's reflected in, say newspaper articles that their parents are reading or commentaries from famous people that are just like, "I don't believe it". And I'm like, "Well just because you don't believe it doesn't mean it doesn't exist" (Elle, she/her, 37, metropolitan Ireland).

Participants also described their discomfort with cisgender creators capitalising off of trans stories in offline media, often using sensationalist storylines. This media, according to Zack, centres “the negatives, or the surgeries, or the gory bits, you know, or they’ll only talk about us when we’re already dead”. William described this kind of content being sought out by cisgender audiences of the film, *Boys Don’t Cry* (1999), who he said watched “because they’re like intrigued and kind of freaked out”. Lefevre (2021) cites this film as an example of trans representation that employs the “reveal scene”, a trope used with the intention of exposing the humanity of a trans character (33). Many participants recounted their perceptions of such tropes, describing how offline media depictions of trans individuals seemed to be tokenistic and perpetuate the narrative that being trans was a tragedy. According to these participants, offline media used trans characters to appear progressive while introducing dramatic storylines in which these characters were condemned to suffer. Zach found such reductionist media depictions of trans lives devaluing of the complexity and breadth of his own experiences as a trans person:

I’m the first to admit that there are things that I’ve experienced as a trans person that I wish I didn’t have to. But I am also so much happier for being a trans person and for having taken those steps to have transitioned (Zach, he/him, 19, metropolitan Ireland).

Liam reflected on these tragic narratives of trans experiences, describing his belief that they contribute to a culture of pessimism and poor mental health among trans people. As Liam explained, “if you’re trans and you’re happy, that’s just not believable”. Elle had a more optimistic view of these narratives, as she believed that negative tropes about queer people had become steadily less prevalent in her lifetime and understood this to be due to the involvement of more queer people in creating offline media. However, most participants agreed that the majority of offline media representations of trans individuals were negative and reductionist. They also discussed their perception of offline media as lacking representations of trans masculinity in particular, a phenomenon that Heinz explores, finding trans masculinity to be “less present, less visible and less familiar in popular consciousness” than trans femininity (Heinz, 2016: 13). In popular media, as Ben put it, “it seems to always be trans women and it seems to always be hateful”. When participants cited rare examples of more nuanced representations of trans individuals, they were often of trans feminine people. For instance, both Liam and Oliver spoke highly of trans actress Laverne Cox’s portrayal of Sophia Burset in *Orange is the New Black* (2013-2019), while expressing disappointment that there wasn’t a similar trans masculine character for them to relate to. “She is a fully fleshed out human-being,” Liam explained, “and that was incredible”.

Although powerful encounters with well-executed trans representation were described, participants found these encounters to be infrequent. Most of the participants referred to a definitive lack of well-developed or high-quality trans masculine representation in general offline media and reported feeling driven to actively seek out representation in response:

Sometimes, I feel like queer people, we have this thing of really enjoying shitty movies just because they have queer people in them. So, I do seek out things that I know I’m going to hate just because I see trans people (William, he/they, 23, metropolitan Ireland).

I actively search out stuff like *Transition of Style Podcast*. I'm not a mad podcast person, but I try and kind of seek out that kind of thing, 'cause, really even in the last year, I've kind of come to a personal realisation that I'm a lot more trans masculine than I ever thought I was. More sort of gender fluid or non-binary in some way. I'm not entirely sure where I sit in that, so obviously the desire is there for me to seek out more of that content, to actually find people who are a little bit more like me that I can relate to (Elle, she/her, 37, metropolitan Ireland).

While most participants described nuanced examples of trans representation as being important to them, Sean, a transsexual man who described his gender as binary, had a different perspective. Although he agreed that there is a lack of trans representation in offline media, he did not necessarily want or see a need for more varied examples of trans experience:

To be honest, I don't even think about it. Again, it goes back to, I mean, I'm walking through the world now as a man and unless something does pop up in the media, I don't think about being trans. I watch TV because I want to watch TV... I would challenge the point of how are you ever going to represent every single person? (Sean, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

Meaningful engagement with offline media representations of trans identities

Offline media representations of trans people were understood by most participants to have the potential to affirm and facilitate recognition of trans viewers' own identities. However, this potential is limited, for, as Lovelock (2017) describes, this representation frequently offers only a "select vision of transgender existence" that meets standards of visibility to a presumed white, cisgender audience (751). Participants with existing trans and/or queer communities reported having less dependence on media representations for validation or guidance, yet they acknowledged offline media's capacity to influence younger trans individuals or trans individuals without support networks. Multiple participants expressed a wish for more nuanced representation and information when they were younger to aid them in early self-identification as trans, as well as to demonstrate the diversity of trans journeys. As Zach described, "if there had been a representation of somebody with the language and explanation, then I could have kind of grabbed onto that and understood it." For Ben, who described his gender as gendervoid and "mostly masc", access to information and representation is especially vital for gender-variant children. Ze spoke of his attempts to run away as a child and feelings of isolation due to a lack of support system. Because of his experience, ze was writing a children's book to "show trans kids that they can love themselves even if nobody else does".

For other participants who did not have an expansive queer network, offline media functioned as a means of experiencing community and helped them learn about specific aspects of living as a trans masculine person. For example, Liam described his experience watching an episode of *Queer Eye* (2018) which featured Skyler Jay, an American trans man, as influencing his journey with trans masculine fashion:

Oh, when he got his properly fitted suit! I went, “I can get a properly fitted suit!” [...] And, for some reason, that just didn’t occur to me. I mean, cis guys get suits tailored to fit them, why wouldn’t a trans guy. But seeing that was eye-opening (Liam, he/him, 25, rural Ireland).

Most participants recounted personal experiences of seeing themselves reflected through offline media representations and finding these experiences instrumental in their exploration of gender. For instance, Elle described the experience of reading about genderqueer masculinity in books such as *Stone Butch Blues* (1993) and *Butch is a Noun* (2006) as helping her understand her own masculinity. Other participants emphasised the pleasure and validation they experienced in relating to on-screen characters when encountering trans storylines in films and television programmes:

Whenever I re-watch *One Day at a Time*, and I just see the first scene where Syd and Syd's friends introduce themselves with their pronouns... every time I watch that I'm just like, “Oh!” Especially when there's a friend who uses ze/zir pronouns... just showing someone who uses neopronouns outside he, she or they, was so good to me. It's a very minor character. We never see them again, but just having it there was like a really defining moment for me. It made me feel more secure (Ben, ze/hir, 23, rural Ireland).

There’s a trans masculine person in the Netflix *Sabrina* show and I love their character. I love their whole plot about trying to use magic to look more masculine and it backfiring... I was 14 when I came out. So, I relate to being at that point in my teenage years, being really desperate to just look like the other men around me and to fit in with the other men around me even though I couldn't do anything about it (Zach, he/him, 19, metropolitan Ireland).

For William, encountering trans individuals in offline media aided in offsetting internalised, negative feelings around his identity. He described a sense of belonging that occurred while viewing gender-variant individuals in films:

Just 'cause it makes you feel seen obviously, and it makes me still feel... I still have that feeling of sometimes not liking myself for being trans. So when I see people I'm like, “It's okay. There's people out there who are like me, I can see it.” It's not like... I'm not *wrong* (William, he/they, 23, metropolitan Ireland).

Multiple participants discussed the ways offline media representations of trans people could act as a platform for discussion with cisgender people, including their families and friends. Participants highlighted that, for closeted trans individuals especially, engaging with others through offline media could initiate pivotal conversations and generate more understanding:

I actually brought a book [*Trans Mission: My Quest to a Beard* (2017)] with me, in my bag, it’s about a guy from England and his journey through his transition. I pick up kind of tips from that, because, well, my mother doesn’t actually accept my transition, so I’ve actually kind of picked out bits and reworded them to write a letter that I haven’t actually given to her yet. But I’m planning on giving it to her because I don’t think that she actually understands (Oliver, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

If you're watching a TV show and there just happens to be a trans character on it, then that could actually start a conversation with people that could actually bring it into their lives because you're not putting it in front of them specifically because you want to talk about being trans. It's just 'cause it's telly, you're just watching some shows and that could start a conversation for you with your family that could open things up for you (Zach, he/him, 19, metropolitan Ireland).

Recent scholarship around trans representation has explored how increased visibility has been accompanied by a rising number of attacks against trans people (Stanley, 2021; cárdenas 2019; Gossett et al., 2019). While the threat of such violence was ever-present in participants' reports of their daily interactions, it was notable that some participants described using media as a way of measuring safety. Participants described using conversations around trans representation to help gauge people's views of trans individuals without, as William explained, "endangering or outing yourself". Liam recounted his confidence in coming out to his mother due to her positive reaction to trans characters on television:

But had my mother been like, "That's gross" or something, that would have been something that I now know, that coming out would have been that bit harder (Liam, he/him, 25, rural Ireland).

Binary masculinity in offline media representations of identity

Throughout the interviews, a topic that emerged as significant to each of the participants was the way offline media presented gender in general, beyond a specific portrayal of trans masculinity. As our conversations exposed, media representations of hegemonic masculinity played a role in these individuals' embodied experiences of gender. As Connell and Messerschmidt describe, "hegemonic masculinity is related to particular ways of representing and using men's bodies" (2005: 850), and offline media representations of masculinity are often centred on bodily strength and sexual appeal to women. Participants described the pressures of meeting such cis/heteronormative standards of appearance:

If you see a cis man in the media and they're all very muscular and they have a lot of facial hair, or a beard, that kind of puts pressure on a trans person that is trying to look masculine, to be able to meet the same standard as the men that we see in the media (Oliver, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

Trans masculine people that you'll see in media are like that guy Aydian Dowling, he was on the cover of *Men's Health* and he was all ripped and everything... So, that makes me feel a lot of pressure to do that kind of thing. And I can't tell if I actually *want* to be fit or if I just wanted to put myself in a safe kind of territory (William, he/they, 23, metropolitan Ireland).

For most participants, cis/heteronormative standards around emotional behaviour felt especially emphasised within the binary gender system upheld in offline media. These participants described their resistance to meeting societal expectations of the unemotional, misogynist and aggressive models of masculinity most often represented:

It sucks as well because everyone then is just like, “Well if you're masculine then you're much tougher. So why are you crying?” Because that's not what butches do. And that's such bullshit because we're just humans as well (Elle, she/her, 37, metropolitan Ireland).

I find that, coming from growing up and being socialised as a woman where I was allowed to cry and laugh, now I feel like I really can't do those things... And it's an unspoken feeling of “this is how you are a man”. Where I feel like when I was a woman, I felt more freedom (William, he/they, 23, metropolitan Ireland).

A lot of that stereotypically masculine stuff is not healthy. It's a lot of toxic behaviours and stuff that isn't good for you. Like not talking about your feelings, and being a misogynist, and stuff like that (Zach, he/him, 19, metropolitan Ireland).

Participants described experiencing pressure to meet these cisnormative standards of masculinity in order to “pass”. Passing, as described by Moriel (2005), is “the movement from one identity group to another, usually from margin to mainstream” (167). To “pass”, a trans individual must be perceived as cisgender by others. For trans individuals, the ability to find acceptance and safety within society is often contingent on this perception. Several participants discussed the emotional impact of trying to pass through performances of normative masculinity:

I would be so much happier if I looked more masculine, and if I had facial hair, or was taller. Yeah, but I don't. But I know other people would be more comfortable if I did. Because then they could forget that I'm trans and focus on the fact that I'm a guy (Liam, he/him, 25, rural Ireland).

It's hard for a trans guy to pass as being cis. Like, if you're walking down the street, or... I was on the bus the other day with a friend and someone asked was I a girl or a boy. And that really upset me. So, I kind of do things to try to look more masculine (Oliver, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

Transnormativity in offline media representations of trans identities

While many participants described their struggles to feel accepted within a broader cis/heteronormative society, most found that experiences of trans masculinity which diverged from transnormative narratives were less accepted within queer communities as well. In our interview, William described the dominant offline media narrative as suggesting trans people are “trapped in the wrong body,” which implies that trans bodies are inherently “wrong”. Mozer (2021) calls this the “grand narrative” in which trans experiences are lumped together to form a reproducible storyline that operates to “make sense” of trans identity through a gender-normative lens (17). As Johnson asserts, the inclusion of this narrative in trans masculine media promotes and standardises trans medical interventions (2016: 485). Yet, for William, who has had top surgery (reconstructive chest surgery) and has experienced gender dysphoria, offline media's presentation of gender-affirming treatments as remedying something “wrong” did not speak to the complexity of trans experience:

I don't think that my body is wrong. I actually am alright with the idea of changing my body. I don't hate my body all the time, but people have this idea [...] that trans people always have to feel sad and if you're seen to be enjoying yourself, they're kind of like, "Oh, but aren't you thinking about how you don't have a penis?" (William, he/they, 23, metropolitan Ireland).

Trans masculine imagery in media is often centred around postsurgical scars that signify top surgery, which Heinz describes as "perhaps the most normative symbolic representation of transmasculinity" (2016: 105). This portrayal of medicalised trans experience reinforces transnormative understandings of identity, which, as participants suggested, influences how other people conceptualise and interact with trans individuals. Most participants described how offline media trans narratives often centred binary trans experiences, and that the Irish trans community appeared to uphold medical transition as the most legitimate trans experience:

There's a lot of commentary and stuff about how, for example, you have to experience gender dysphoria to be trans, to identify as trans in some way. Or you have to want to have top surgery. Or you have to want to do x, y, z. You have to want to take testosterone. And that's really scary because then you start to question yourself and you're going, "If I don't want to do those things, then can I really take on this label? Is that really me? Am I just making something up in my head?" (Elle, she/her, 37, metropolitan Ireland).

I am very open and broad about what I believe trans identity can look like and what I believe gender is like. And there are some trans people who are not. There are some trans people who are very set in their rigid ideas of a gender binary and gender stereotypes, which is totally beyond me as to why you would want to do that, when that exact system has caused so many problems for you (Zach, he/him, 19, metropolitan Ireland).

Sean's opinions on gender reflected this schism within the trans community, as he did not associate his experience as a transsexual person with the experiences of non-binary trans people who do not seek gender-affirming medical care:

I separate those two so much because it is two completely different experiences. Like someone just cutting their hair and fighting for trans rights and that's it. I don't know, opposed to someone who's actually gone through the emotional stuff and no one talks about the after effect, the socialisation effect of after you go through all the hormones and stuff. But that's the hardest part that I had (Sean, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

As Liam described, however, not conforming to what is seen as "the right way to be trans masculine," is not always due to personal sense of identity. For him, disability prevented him from binding his chest and presenting as a binary trans masculine person, a fact which was only made more distressing by other trans people enforcing transnormative standards:

I used to not bind. As I've said, I have a disability, and anything constricting my ribs is not great, but the more people fixated on the fact that I didn't bind,

the more I felt I had to. And now it's completely unbearable to not bind (Liam, he/him, 25, rural Ireland).

The majority of participants described transnormative trans experiences as being privileged within society, and even weaponised by binary trans individuals against gender-non-conforming trans individuals. Sean, however, viewed gender-non-conforming trans individuals as being politically aligned and intolerant of binary trans individuals. Sean described the “politicisation” of trans identity, both among the trans community in Ireland and what is reflected in offline media, as being extremely alienating. He positioned his medical transition as a legitimising experience which made him transsexual rather than transgender, a label he associated with political identity:

I was transgender and now 'cause I've transitioned, I'm a transsexual. I do make that distinction because *they* don't represent me. I don't mind them doing whatever they're doing, but just don't push the political aspect into transgenderism. Because it's not political. It's a medical, it's a real life medical condition that people have to suffer with (Sean, he/him, 21, rural Ireland).

Transnormative representations of medicalised gender-variance can be viewed as examples of what Keegan calls “‘good’ trans objects” (2022). These are the trans characters and storylines that are marketable within the normative, white supremacist, binary gender system. While Sean’s experience is legible within this framework, most of the other participants’ experiences of gender threaten to unsettle it. For William, it was these potentially disruptive aspects of his identity that made him proud to be trans. He described how the frequent depiction of normative, medicalised trans identities in offline media was something that troubled him:

And that's how the mainstream media is going with trans people. By sanitising trans masculine identities, I think, it's just removing the radical part of being trans, and I think it is really radical to be trans (William, he/they, 23, rural Ireland).

Conclusion

In this time of “trans visibility” (Gossett et al., 2019: xv), trans characters, celebrities, and storylines are getting more exposure than ever before. However, according to the Irish trans masculine individuals interviewed for this study, this representation remains unnuanced. Trans content and characters were perceived by them as uncommon, and when this content did feature in offline media, the representations were not usually regarded as being relatable or validating to participants; they were more often experienced as devaluing of their own identities. Participants described using existing offline media representations of trans identities as sites of self-reflection and initiating dialogue with others, yet described these opportunities as limited by the lack of diverse, authentic representations of trans masculine life. These findings expose the meaningful role that representation can play in trans lives, while also highlighting issues posed by the promotion of trans representation rendered “respectable” within hierarchical, racialised systems of gender and sexuality. As Faye reminds us, while visibility can be viewed as having improved the lives of some trans people in minimal ways, the extent of this improvement has been

“vastly overstated” (2021: 11). This study’s findings similarly suggest that trans representation should not be viewed as a revolutionary tool. In fact, trans visibility has been shown to occur in parallel to increased anti-trans violence and surveillance (Faye, 2021; R. Gossett et al., 2019). For many participants, media portrayals of trans identities were associated with feelings of unsafety and unbelonging. Their descriptions of encounters with transnormative representations of gender-variance portrayed the regulatory function such media can have.

As one participant eloquently remarked, by “removing the radical” from representations of trans identities, offline media reinforces the narrative of a monolithic, transnormative experience. According to most of the individuals interviewed, popular offline media’s reductionist trans narratives did not encompass the wide-ranging experiences and identities of trans individuals. While one participant had the impression that non-binary trans people were overrepresented within the trans community in Ireland, most of the individuals interviewed described a lack of non-binary representation that resonated with their own experiences of gender. As cárdenas (2019) describes, “the increasing mainstream visibility of transgender people has been brought about by solidifying the line between who is an acceptable trans person and who is disposable” (170). For the trans masculine individuals interviewed, being “acceptable” meant being legible as a binary man within systems of hegemonic masculinity. Representations of such binary performances of masculinity in offline media were discussed by many of the participants, who did not relate to this presentation of gender and described feeling pressured to re-enact normative masculinity as a means of acceptance and safety. Yet, most of the individuals interviewed described experiencing their identities as resisting the boundaries imposed by the gender binary, whether by existing in a body that could not be binarily sexed, or by refusing to perform gender through models of binary masculinity.

This article does not attempt to present a cohesive trans masculine experience. Indeed, the lack of non-white participants in this study is a significant limitation that further studies of trans masculinities in Ireland should address. This study serves as a foundation for future research around trans masculine people’s experiences with media representations of trans identities and masculinities, and the role of popular media in the lives of trans individuals. The objective of this study was to investigate how trans masculine people living in Ireland perceive and engage with representations of trans identities in different outlets of popular offline media. Exploring the tensions between trans visibility, representation, and increasing anti-trans rhetoric and violence, this study found that the majority of participants, while able to have meaningful encounters with exceptional trans representation, perceived offline media representations of trans identities to be uncommon. When representations did occur, most participants found them to be tokenistic, reductionist and sensationalist in general. Further, most participants found the prevailing narratives of these representations to uphold binary masculinity and transnormativity. While many participants expressed a wish for more nuanced reflections of trans experience in popular media, their experiences with existing trans representation conveyed its limits as a tool for social progress. For most of the participants, offline media contributed to the policing of their genders in tangible ways, a phenomenon which unsettles the comforting idea that increased trans representation will lead the way to liberation.

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